

Laryngoscopic View and Ease of Intubation: A Comparison of McCoy, Macintosh and Airtraq Laryngoscopes in Predicted Difficult Airway

Orshio DU¹, Nuhu SI², Embu YH², Isamade SE², Usman YM³, Abdullahi AM⁴

¹ Department of Anaesthesia and Critical Care, Federal Medical Centre Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria

² Department of Anaesthetics, University of Jos, Nigeria.

³ Department of Human Anatomy, University of Jos, Nigeria.

⁴ Department of Anaesthesia, Critical Care and Pain Management, Jos University Teaching Hospital, Jos.

Correspondence: Orshio UD, Department of Anaesthesia and Critical Care, Federal Medical Centre, Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria.

E-mail: donaldorshio@gmail.com Phone: +234(0)8034210280

Article information

Date Submitted: 06/02/2024

Date Accepted: 12/10/2024

Date Published: 18/12/2024

ABSTRACT

Difficult airway management using direct laryngoscopes such as McCoy and Macintosh for tracheal intubation, remains a challenge to the Anaesthetist due to difficulty in alignment of the oral, pharyngeal and laryngeal axes. The Airtraq, a video laryngoscope, reduces this difficulty, improving laryngoscopic view and ease of intubation. This study sought to compare laryngoscopic view, ease of intubation and haemodynamic changes using McCoy, Macintosh as well as Airtraq Laryngoscopes in adult patients with predicted difficult airway. After obtaining ethical clearance, 93 consenting adult patients with predicted difficult airway requiring general anaesthesia with endotracheal intubation were randomly assigned to these three groups. Laryngoscopic view, ease of intubation and haemodynamic changes during laryngoscopy and intubation were assessed and recorded. The study participants were comparable across the study groups. There was a significant statistical difference in laryngoscopic view between study groups with thirty (96.8%) patients in the Airtraq group having Cormack and Lehane (CL) grade 1, compared to thirteen (41.9%) patients in the McCoy group and the Macintosh group having nine (29.0%) patients ($p=0.001$). The ease of intubation showed that 28 (90.3%), 11 (35.5%) and 8 (25.8%) patients in the Airtraq, McCoy and Macintosh groups respectively had an IDS score of 0 ($p=0.001$). The Airtraq laryngoscope was superior to both the McCoy and Macintosh laryngoscopes in improving laryngoscopic view and ease of intubation. The haemodynamic changes due to laryngoscopy and intubation were comparable among the three groups.

Keywords: Airtraq, Difficult airway, Laryngoscopic view, Macintosh, McCoy

INTRODUCTION

Difficult airway is one of the clinical scenarios encountered by Anaesthetists in the practice of anaesthesia in patients that require airway management. The incidence of difficult airway is high especially in

low resource settings accounting for up to 1 in 100 cases in emergency obstetrics practice.¹ It has been reported to be as high as 10% in obstetric patients in Lagos University Teaching Hospital.²

Difficult airway or intubation can either be predicted or

How to cite this article

*Orshio DU, Nuhu SI, Embu YH, Isamade SE, Usman YM, Abdullahi AM. Laryngoscopic View and Ease of Intubation: A Comparison of McCoy, Macintosh and Airtraq Laryngoscopes in Predicted Difficult Airway Patients. *J Biomed Res Clin Pract*: 2024;7(4):00-00. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609701>.

Access to the article

Website: <http://www.jbrcp.org>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14609701

unpredicted.³ A common factor that prevents successful tracheal intubation is the inability to visualise the vocal cords during direct laryngoscopy.⁴

Failure to provide a patent airway at any step of general anaesthesia can lead to devastating complications,⁵ such as hypoxic brain injury, aspiration pneumonitis, major airway trauma, oesophageal intubation, and even death.⁶ Thus, the management of the difficult airway is an important skill desirable for every Anaesthetist. The gold standard for difficult airway management requires the use of fibre-optic laryngoscope (FOL) or video laryngoscope such as the Airtraq.⁷

This study therefore sought to determine and compare laryngoscopic views, ease of intubation and haemodynamic changes during laryngoscopy using McCoy, Macintosh as well as Airtraq laryngoscopes in adult patients with predicted difficult airway.

METHODOLOGY

This was a comparative randomized prospective study that was conducted in the Jos University Teaching Hospital, North-central Nigeria in a six-month period. Patients recruited into this study were all American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) physical status I and II with Mallampati class III and IV, aged between 18 and 60 years. Patients with risk for aspiration, limited mouth opening, neck mass, short neck, oropharyngeal tumours, cervical spine abnormalities, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, asthma, BMI greater than 35kg/m², or those who did not consent to the study were excluded.

Sampling was done by a blind process where the different groups were written and deposited in an opaque envelope. Patients were allotted to a particular group as chosen such as A, B and C as the case may be. Group A was for McCoy, while groups B and C were for Macintosh and Airtraq respectively.

The sample size for this study was estimated from the formula for comparing different proportions

across groups.⁸ With a 95% confidence interval and 80% power of the study corresponding to $Z_{\alpha/2} = 1.96$ and $Z_{\beta} = 0.84$, P1 and P2 were assumed from a previous study⁹ to be 95% and 65% respectively. This gives a sample size of 93 patients with 31 patients per group assuming a

10% attrition rate.

All patients were visited a day before surgery for pre-operative assessment including airway assessment and informed consent obtained. They all had their investigations reviewed. Patients were fasted before surgery according to standard fasting guidelines. Demographic data such as age, sex, weight and height were collected during the pre-operative visit. Anxiolytic premedication (oral diazepam 10mg) was given to all patients the night before surgery at bed time.

On the morning of the surgery, the patients were randomised into groups A, B or C as described earlier. Intravenous access was secured with appropriate size intravenous cannula. Standard monitoring like pulse oximetry (SPO₂), electrocardiography (ECG), pulse rate (PR), non-invasive blood pressure (NIBP) [systolic blood pressure {SBP}, diastolic blood pressure {DBP}], mean arterial pressure (MAP), and capnography (EtCO₂) was done using the GE Dash 4000 multi-parameter monitor, (GCX Corporation, United States of America). This device was used to measure the PR, SBP, DBP, MAP, EtCO₂ and SPO₂ at 0 (baseline), and at 1st, 3rd, 5th, 7th and 10th minutes respectively after intubation. Difficult Airway Tray (DAT) containing Classic LMA sizes 3, 4, and 5, gum elastic bougie, nasopharyngeal and oropharyngeal airway, malleable stylet, cricothyrotomy set, a fully charged Airtraq video laryngoscope and a functional high-pressure suction machine for possible emergency management of difficult intubation, was made available.

The patients were placed on the operating table in the supine position with the head slightly elevated with a doughnut pad under the occiput to elevate the head to approximately 7-10 cm while extending the neck from the chest to assume the sniffing position.¹⁰ Pre-oxygenation was done with 100% Oxygen at 6L/m for 3minutes. This was followed by intravenous induction with titrated sleeping dose of IV propofol 2.5mg/kg in a syringe. Mask ventilation was tested when the patient was fully asleep. Any patient in whom mask ventilation was not possible was withdrawn and replaced in the study. The patients with successful mask ventilation were given IV suxamethonium 2mg/kg to facilitate

laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation after 60 seconds of suxamethonium administration.

For the McCoy group, direct laryngoscopy was done using size 4 blade. The flexi tip of the blade was then used to lift the epiglottis when sighted to obtain the desired glottic aperture for CL grading. The necessity for external laryngeal manipulation (ELM), and the position of the vocal cords were noted. The appropriate ETT was then passed. The tube placement was confirmed and secured with an adhesive tape.

If any patient had intubation attempted and his or her SPO₂ went below 92% or the duration of laryngoscopy was prolonged above 120 seconds, failed intubation attempt was declared.^{9,12} Such patient's airway was suctioned for secretions, an oropharyngeal airway inserted and the patient ventilated with 100% oxygen. Isoflurane at 2% was then introduced and the process of intubation was repeated as above for the second time by the supervising Consultant Anaesthetist, using the primary laryngoscope blade, the McCoy laryngoscope, for the group. The number of intubation attempts was noted. Haemodynamic changes were also noted as stated above. The same procedure was carried out for the Macintosh group (B) as described above for the McCoy group (A) but using Macintosh laryngoscope.

For the Airtraq group (C), laryngoscopy and intubation were done using the Airtraq video laryngoscope and appropriately sized endotracheal tube (ETT). The Airtraq device was switched on about 1 minute before intubation to activate the antifogging system. It was then connected to the wireless display camera as the monitor. A well lubricated appropriately sized ETT was then preloaded into the ETT channel of the laryngoscope blade. The laryngoscopic view noticed on the monitor was graded using the CL scale. The ETT was then directed into the glottis through the vocal cords. The ease of intubation was assessed using the IDS score, (Table 3¹⁶). The ETT was detached from the channelled blade and secured at the appropriate level.

The analysis of collected data was done with SPSS 23.0 version. Categorical data was expressed in frequencies and percentages. Continuous data was expressed as

mean \pm standard deviation. The significance of the study was tested with allowable error of 5%. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to compare continuous variables across the groups. Chi-square test was used to find association between the categorical variables. The Fischer's exact test was used to compare qualitative variables. A probability value ($p \leq 0.05$) at 95% confidence interval was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

The study lasted for six months. All 93 enrolled patients were included in the final analysis. The study participants comprised of more females 56 (60.2%) than males 37 (39.8%). The study participants were comparable among the study groups (Table 1). A total of 52 (55.9%) of the predicted difficult airway patients had CL laryngoscopic view grade 1. Forty (43.0%) had CL grade 2 view while only 1 (1.1%) had CL grade 3 view. No patient had CL grade 3 view in the Airtraq group and no patient had CL grade 4 view in any of the three groups (Table 2). The Airtraq group had 28 patients (90.3%) with IDS score of 0 while the McCoy group and the Macintosh groups had 11 (35.5%) and 8 (25.8%) of patients with IDS score of 0 respectively. In all, 6 (6.5%) patients had IDS score of 4, no patient in both the McCoy and Airtraq groups had IDS score of 5, and 1 (3.2%) patient in the Macintosh group had IDS score of 5. This was statistically significant ($p = 0.001$) (Table 3). Thirty (96.8%) patients in the McCoy group were intubated at first attempt, 29 (93.5%) in the Macintosh group and all the 31 (100.0%) patients in the Airtraq group were intubated at first attempt (Table 4). A total of 90 (96.8%) patients had successful intubation at first attempt. One (3.2%) and 2 (6.5%) respectively in the McCoy and Macintosh groups were intubated at second attempt. This was not statistically significant, ($p = 0.770$). All the haemodynamic changes (PR, SBP, DBP, MAP, EtCO₂ and SPO₂) in the study were comparable across the study groups (Figures 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5).

Table 1 Demographic characteristics and ASA classification of patients among the study groups

Variables	Study Groups			Statistics	p-value
	McCoy	Macintosh	Airtraq		
Gender (Number/percent)					
Female	21(67.7)	20(64.5)	15(48.4)	2.783	0.249
Males	10(32.3)	11(35.5)	16(51.6)		
ASA (Number/percent)					
I	10(32.3)	14(45.2)	4(12.9)	7.767	0.021
II	21(67.7)	17(54.8)	27(87.1)		
Age (years) Mean±SD					
	39.06±10.01	43.48±12.43	43.03±11.48	1.423	0.246
Weight (Kg) Mean±SD					
	71.77±14.31	68.23±11.36	69.45±13.17	0.593	0.555
Height (cm) Mean±SD					
	166.32 ±7.91	165.77±5.52	167.68±7.52	0.597	0.553
BMI (Kg/m²) Mean±SD					
	25.88±4.64	24.82±4.07	24.72±4.65	0.644	0.528

Table 2 Comparison of Cormack -Lehane Grades among the study groups

CL Grades (Number/percent)	Study Groups			F-test	p-value
	McCoy	Macintosh	Airtraq		
1	13(41.9)	9(29.0)	30(96.8)	34.396	0.001
2	17(54.8)	22(71.0)	1(3.2)		
3	1(3.2)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)		
4	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)		

*Cormack and Lahane

Table 3: Comparison of Intubation Difficulty Scale scores among the study groups

Variables	Study Groups			Statistics	p-value
	McCoy	Macintosh	Airtraq		
IDS score (Number/percent)					
0	11(35.5)	8(25.8)	28(90.3)	43.208	0.001
1	2(6.5)	3(9.7)	3(9.7)		
2	12(38.7)	6(19.4)	0(0.0)		
3	4(12.9)	9(29.0)	0(0.0)		
4	2(6.5)	4(12.9)	0(0.0)		
5	0(0.0)	1(3.2)	0(0.0)		
IDS Classification (Number/percent)					
0 (Easy Intubation)	11(35.5)	8(25.8)	28(90.3)	30.025	0.001
1-5 (Slight difficulty)	20(64.5)	23(74.2)	3(9.7)		
>5 (Moderate to major difficulty)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)		
∞ (Impossible intubation)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)		

*Intubation Difficulty Scale

Table 4: Intubation attempts and external laryngeal manipulation (ELM) among study groups

Variables	Study Groups			Statistics	p-value
	McCoy	Macintosh	Airtraq		
Intubation attempts (Number/percent)					
1 st Attempt	30(96.8)	29(93.5)	31(100.0)	1.883	0.770
2 nd Attempt	1(3.2)	2(6.5)	0(0.0)		
External laryngeal manipulation (Number/percent)					
Not applied	12(38.7)	17(54.8)	31(100.0)	27.336	0.001
Applied	19(61.3)	14(45.2)	0(0.0)		

Figure 1 Mean pulse rate (bpm) at different time intervals in the study groups

Figure 5 Mean SPO₂ (%) among study groups at different time intervals

Figure 2 Mean SBP and mean DBP (mmHg) of the study groups at different time intervals

Figure 3 Means of MAP (mmHg) of the study groups at different time intervals

Figure 4 Mean EtCO₂ (mmHg) among study groups at different time intervals

DISCUSSION

The patients intubated with the Airtraq laryngoscope had the best laryngoscopic view according to CL grading as all these patients had CL grade 1 followed by the McCoy group and then the Macintosh group. The Airtraq's superiority in producing the best glottis view using CL grading may be due to its inbuilt sets of prisms that enhanced the view without the need for alignment of the oral pharyngeal and laryngeal axes as with the McCoy and the Macintosh blades. The performance of the Airtraq laryngoscope as seen in our study was also observed by Rajendra et al.¹³ All patients intubated with the Airtraq laryngoscope in that study had CL grade 1 while the McCoy and the Macintosh groups produced 70% and 66.7% of patients with CL1 respectively ($p = 0.001$). Szalast et al¹⁴ in their comparison of Airtraq and Macintosh laryngoscopes applied by nurses in manikins with normal and difficult airways, found that in the normal airway scenario, the Airtraq produced 88.9% of patients with CL grade 1 while the Macintosh had 37%. This was significant, ($p = 0.016$). In the difficult airway scenario, there was also a significant difference ($p = 0.001$) in the ability of the Airtraq laryngoscope to produce lower CL grades signifying better laryngoscopic view against the Macintosh. These findings are in line with our study in predicted difficult airway patients.

In similarity to our study, Hosalli et al¹⁵ who studied laryngoscopic view in a randomised clinical trial among 90 patients with cervical spine immobilisation also

found the McCoy laryngoscope to be superior to the Macintosh laryngoscope. This finding may be because of the familiarity of the laryngoscopist with the devices. The ability of the McCoy to flex and elevate the epiglottis for better glottic view unlike the Macintosh laryngoscope is an additional feature that could probably account for the McCoy's better performance over the Macintosh in grading laryngoscopic view.

This study found that the ease of intubation according to IDS score by Adnet et al^{16,17} was easy (0 score) in almost all the patients intubated using the Airtraq laryngoscope followed by the McCoy and then the Macintosh laryngoscopes. All the patients were intubated successfully and no moderate to major difficulty at intubation (score >5) was noticed in any of the study groups. Our study therefore demonstrated the superiority of the Airtraq laryngoscope over the McCoy and the Macintosh in improving the ease of intubation. This is similar to findings reported by Hosalli et al¹⁵ who found that the IDS scores in their patients who had cervical spine immobilisation, mimicking difficult airway were significantly lower in the Airtraq laryngoscope. Maharaj et al⁹ also had successful first intubation attempts achieved with the use of Airtraq laryngoscope in 95% of difficult airway patients compared to 65% with the Macintosh laryngoscope.

While our study found that no ELM was required during intubation of the patients in the Airtraq group, it was applied in both the McCoy and Macintosh groups with the McCoy group requiring more ELM application compared to the Macintosh laryngoscope. The flexi-tip design of the McCoy blade should normally help in reducing the application of ELM especially in experienced hands. However, in this index study, the laryngoscopist had little prior experience with the McCoy laryngoscope and this could probably account for the increased requirement for the application of ELM. In spite of the rigid design of the Macintosh blade, the laryngoscopist's better experience with it compared to the McCoy blade reduced the necessity for the application of ELM in the Macintosh group. It could also be probably due to the higher number of Mallampati IV patients in the McCoy group (though not

statistically significant) that could have accounted for the greater requirement for ELM in the McCoy group compared to the Macintosh group. Sahoo and colleagues¹⁸ compared ease of intubation in difficult airway patients with Mallampati grades III or IV using the Airtraq and McCoy laryngoscopes. They found statistically significant difference, ($p < 0.005$) between the two groups. The ease of intubation was far better with the Airtraq than the McCoy. They had 93.33% of the difficult airway patients successfully intubated with the Airtraq without external aid compared to only 66.67% in the McCoy group that did not require external aid for intubation. This showed that the Airtraq was better than the McCoy laryngoscope in terms of ease of intubation. Bhandari et al¹⁹ also found that the ease of intubation was better with the Airtraq group which had 97.5% of patients with easy intubation compared to the 42.5% of patients in the Macintosh group. Nuhu et al.²⁰ however found comparable ease of intubation between the Airtraq and the Macintosh in patients undergoing tracheal intubation with simulated cervical spine immobilisation.

Concerning haemodynamic responses in patients during intubation, the present study did not find any significant difference between the McCoy, Macintosh and Airtraq laryngoscopes. The mean baseline PR, SBP, DBP, MAP, EtCO₂ and SPO₂ at the different time intervals were comparable. This finding is however in contrast to the studies by both Maharaj et al⁹ on one hand and Rayavarapu and Dhorigol¹⁷ on the other, who found significantly higher rise in blood pressure in the patients intubated with Macintosh than with Airtraq. Unlike this current study, Paul and Nathroy²¹ just like Jitendra et al²² also found a significant difference in the PR of their patients as those intubated with the McCoy exhibited significantly lower PR changes compared to the Macintosh laryngoscope. It is known that laryngoscopy and intubation result in increased plasma nor-adrenaline and adrenaline levels thereby causing a rise in heart rate and mean arterial pressure.⁹ The type of laryngoscope blade used influences the degree of hemodynamic response due to mechanical stimulation.²³ During laryngoscopy with the Macintosh laryngoscope, the

rigid blade has to displace the tongue to the left and lift the epiglottis with an upward lifting force exerted at the vallecula in order to align the oral pharyngeal and laryngeal axes. For better view, the force exerted at the base of the tongue can be as high as 30 to 50 Newtons (N) when the Macintosh laryngoscope is used.²⁴ The McCoy blade uses a levering action and flexes the tip like a hinge thereby reducing the force exerted during laryngoscopy and intubation.²⁵ The force exerted by the Airtraq according to Hindman et al²⁴ is much lower because it enables glottis visualization without aligning the anatomical axes.

CONCLUSION

The study showed that there was significant difference in the laryngoscopic view and the ease of intubation when the McCoy, Macintosh and Airtraq laryngoscopes were compared in adult patients with predicted difficult airway. The Airtraq laryngoscope had the best laryngoscopic view followed by the McCoy. The ease of intubation was also best with the Airtraq laryngoscope, equally followed by the McCoy. The haemodynamic changes due to laryngoscopy and intubation were comparable among the three groups.

Recommendations

1. Deliberate policies should be put in place to make Airtraq laryngoscopes available in all hospitals where surgeries requiring general anaesthesia and tracheal intubation are practiced.
2. Training of anaesthetists on the use of Airtraq laryngoscope will also improve its operational skills and reduce the morbidity and mortality associated with failed airway management.

Limitations

1. It was not possible to blind the laryngoscopist to the type of laryngoscope that was used for laryngoscopy in the study groups. This could be a source of bias.
2. The non-use of antisialogue premedication necessitating regular suctioning could trigger the release of catecholamine and this could have affected some haemodynamic changes.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank the patients who volunteered to participate in this study without which the study would have not been possible.

Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Cook TM, MacDougall-Davis SR. Complications and failure of airway management. *Br J Anaesth.* 2012; 1: 68–85.
2. Merah NA, Foulkes-Crabbe DJ, Kushimo OT, Ajayi PA. Prediction of difficult laryngoscopy in a population of Nigerian obstetric patients. *West Afr J Med.* 2004; 23(1): 38-41.
3. Nwasor EO, Lawal AT. Use of Laryngeal Mask Airway in the management of a difficult airway: A case report. *Open Anesthesiol J.* 2013; 3: 97-101.
4. Arshad Z, Abbas H, Bogra J, Saxena S. Comparison of laryngoscopic view and hemodynamic changes with flexitip McCoy and Macintosh laryngoscope blade in predicted easy and difficult airway. *Open Anesthesiol J.* 2013; 3: 278-282.
5. Cook TM. A new practical classification of laryngeal view. *Anaesthesia.* 2000; 55: 274–279.
6. Bolaji BO, Suleiman ZA, Adegboye MB, Agodirin OS, Olatoke SA, Habeeb OG et al. Goitre Related Factors for Predicting Difficult Intubation in Patients Scheduled for Thyroidectomy in a Resource Challenged Health Institution in North Central Nigeria. *Ethiop J Health Sci.* 2018; 28(2): 169-177.
7. Nwasor EO, Olateju SO, Kalu QN. Airway management: A survey of training and Practices of Nigerian anaesthetists. *Nig J Clin Pract.* 2014; 17(5): 569-572.
8. Charan J, Biswas T. How to calculate sample size for different study designs in medical research. [Indian J Psychol Med.](#) 2013; 35(2): 121–126.
9. Maharaj CH, Costello JF, Harte BH, Laffey JG. Evaluation of Airtraq and Macintosh laryngoscopes in patients at increased risk for difficult tracheal

- intubation. *Anaesthesia*. 2008; 63:182-188.
10. Pal R, Chauhan S, Ved BK, Lad SR. Evaluation of laryngoscopic view, intubation difficulty and sympathetic response during direct laryngoscopy in sniffing position and simple head extension: a prospective and randomised comparative study. *Int J Res Med Sci*. 2015; 3 (8): 1895-1901.
 11. Gupta S and Kirubahar R. A comparative study of intubating conditions of rocuronium bromide and suxamethonium in adult patients. *Anesth Essays Res*. 2010; 4(1):15-19.
 12. Aqil M. A study of stress response to endotracheal intubation comparing Glidescope and flexible fibreoptic bronchoscope. *Pak J Med Sci*. 2014; 30(5): 1001-1006.
 13. Rajendra N, Krishnamurthy D, Madhusudhana R, Nelemangala K. A comparative study of laryngoscopic view and intubation response using Macintosh, McCoy and Airtraq laryngoscopes in adults undergoing elective surgeries. *Indian J Anaesth Analg*. 2020; 7(4): 1011-1018.
 14. Szalast P, Smereka J, Ruetzler K, Makomaska-Szarkoszyk E, Kranc K, et al. Comparison of Airtraq and Macintosh laryngoscope applied by Nurses in manikins with normal and difficult airway: pilot data. *Post N Med* 2018; 31 (5): 248-253.
 15. Hosalli V, Arjun BK, Ambi U, Hulakund S. Comparison of Airtraq™, McCoy™ and Macintosh laryngoscopes for endotracheal intubation in patients with cervical spine immobilisation: A randomised clinical trial. *Indian J Anaesth*. 2017; 61: 332-337.
 16. Adnet F, Borron SW, Racine S.X, Clemessy J, Fournier J, Plaisance P. The intubation difficulty scale (IDS) proposal and evaluation of a new score characterising the complexity of endotracheal intubation. *Anesthesiology*. 1997; 87: 1290-1297.
 17. Rayavarapu A, Dhorigol MG. Comparison of glottic view during intubation using Airtraq and Macintosh laryngoscopes in adult patients undergoing surgeries under general anaesthesia with a simulated cervical spine immobilisation: A one-year hospital based randomised controlled trial. *Indian J Health Sci Biomed Res* 2017; 10: 84-89.
 18. Sahoo AK, Majihi K, Mandal I. A comparative evaluation of haemodynamic response and ease of intubation using Airtraq and McCoy laryngoscope. *Anesth Essays Res* 2019; 13: 498-502.
 19. Bhandari G, Shahi KS, Asad M, Bhakuni R. Airtraq versus Macintosh laryngoscope: A comparative study of tracheal intubation. *Anesth Essays Res*. 2013; 7 (2): 232-236.
 20. Nuhu SI, Buma GB, Embu HY, Isamade ES, Usman YM. Comparison of Airtraq Laryngoscope and Macintosh Laryngoscope in Patients Undergoing tracheal intubation with simulated Cervical Spine immobilisation. *Journal of Health Sciences and practice* 2023; 1(2): 94-100
 21. Paul A, Nathroy A. Comparison of hemodynamic changes during laryngoscopy with McCoy and Macintosh laryngoscopes. *J Health Res Rev*. 2017; 4: 35-39.
 22. Jitendra M, Sharma S, Katoch M, Gulati S, Gupta H. Comparison of haemodynamic response to tracheal intubation with Macintosh and McCoy laryngoscopes. *J of Evolution of Med Dent Sci* 2015; 4(50): 8676-8684.
 23. Ali QE, Amir SH, Ahmad S. A comparative evaluation of King Vision Video laryngoscope (channelled blade), McCoy, and Macintosh laryngoscopes for tracheal intubation in patients with immobilised cervical spine. *Sri Lankan J Anaesthesiol*. 2017; 25 (2): 70-75.
 24. Hindman BJ, Santoni BG, Puttlitz CM, From RP, Todd MM. Laryngoscopic force and cervical spine motion during intubation with Macintosh and Airtraq laryngoscopes. *Anesthesiology* 2014; 121: 260-262.
 25. Gotiwale K, Lele S, Setiya S. Stress response to laryngoscopy and ease of intubation: Comparison between Macintosh and (levering) McCoy's type laryngoscope. *Int J Res Med Sci*. 2016; 4(8): 3141-3145.